

D2.6 - Ceramic wastes and by-products properties database

WP 2, T 2.6

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Executive summary

This document is the deliverable “D2.6 / Ceramic wastes and by-products properties database” of the eLITHE project (project reference: 101138325). The main body of this deliverable is represented by the openly accessible database of waste material properties, which has been compiled gathering experimental data during T2.6. The database is accessible via a dedicated link ([e-LITHE Material Summary D2.6.xlsx](#)). This deliverable serves as a summary of the database highlighting the key properties.

The main goal of T2.6 - New circular materials for High Temperature TES: Material sampling collection and characterization is to provide a comprehensive characterization of the waste materials, as received from the project's partners. This characterization is meant to serve as a basis for the later activities planned in WP3 aimed at identifying the main opportunities for upcycling of some of the characterized waste streams as materials suitable for thermal energy storage applications (T3.3).

First the considered materials, as received by project's partners, are listed and described including different ceramic wastes and ashes. Slags from different metallic production processes are also included as comparative materials, often considered for thermal energy storage applications. Secondly, the performed tests are described with their key parameters. To maximize the interpretation and usability of the database, the same information is also included in a dedicated sheet presenting all of the project metadata. Finally, the main results describing density, specific heat, thermal conductivity, displacement under compression load, thermo-gravimetric assessment and compatibility with ternary molten salts are summarized. The results gathered so far refers to first thermal cycles, further results under cyclic operations will be gathered in the following tasks (T3.2).

The obtained data highlights the potential of waste ceramic material, especially clinker wastes, to be exploited, as received, for thermal energy storage applications. Further characterization will be performed in the context of WP3 and the potential storage design to be integrated within the ceramic industries and production lines to maximize flexibility will be performed in T3.3.

The delivery of this deliverable is done in accordance with the description in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A with no time deviation and no content deviation from the original planning.

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ACRONYM LIST

Table 1: Acronym List

Acronym	Definition
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
DSC	Differential scanning calorimetry
TPS	Transient plane source
RH	Relative humidity
TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
MS	Molten salts

1 Introduction

eLITHE aims to **decarbonise the ceramic industry** by demonstrating cost-effective and sustainable electrification of high-temperature thermal processes. To achieve this goal, the project will implement innovative technologies such as **microwave-based furnaces, hybrid tunnel kilns, and advanced smelters**, and test them at three pilot sites.

The main body of this deliverable is represented by the openly accessible database of waste material properties, which has been compiled gathering experimental data during T2.6. The database is accessible via a dedicated link ([eLITHE Material Summary D2.6.xlsx](#)). This deliverable serves as a summary of the database highlighting the key properties.

The main goal of T2.6 New circular materials for High Temperature thermal energy storage (TES): Material sampling collection and characterization is to provide a comprehensive characterization of the waste materials, as received from the project's partners. This characterization is meant to serve as a basis for the later activities aimed at: 1) further characterizing the waste materials under cyclic operation and identifying some potential material postprocessing to maximize their characteristics (T3.2), and 2) design thermal energy storage units including such materials to be potentially deployed within the ceramic industry to maximize its process flexibility (T3.3).

The deliverable is organized in three main sections. First the considered materials, as received by project's partners, are listed and described including different ceramic wastes and ashes. Slags from different metallic production processes are also included as comparative materials, often considered for thermal energy storage applications. Secondly, the performed tests are described with their key parameters. To maximize the interpretation and usability of the database, the same information is also included in a dedicated sheet presenting all the project metadata. Finally, the main results describing density, specific heat, thermal conductivity, displacement under compression load, thermo-gravimetric assessment and compatibility with ternary molten salts are summarized.

The obtained data highlights the potential of waste ceramic material, especially clinker wastes, to be exploited, as received, for thermal energy storage applications.

1.1 Considered waste materials

The materials characterized include 3 waste ceramics received from IZF, 2 ashes from Torrecid and 3 metallic slags that are used for benchmarking as shown in Table 2. The 3 ceramics are clinker, roof tiles and hollow bricks which are all received, from IZF, as broken pieces all particles in a similar size range of 10 to 100 mm. The ashes were received, from

Torrecid, in powder form (wet and dry) which would require the addition of binders in order to be used in packed bed TES applications. For this reason, the characterization is mainly focused on the 3 ceramics that can be used as received. Steel, copper and brass slags are analyzed as benchmarking materials since they are widely considered for TES applications.

Table 2: Waste materials summary

Clinker (IZF)	Roof tiles (IZF)	Hollow bricks (IZF)
Dry ash (Torrecid)	Wet ash (Torrecid)	
Reference materials for benchmarking		
Steel slags	Copper slags	Brass slags

2 Material characterizations

This section provides a short summary of the methods used to characterize the aforementioned waste materials and reference materials. All discussed information are also included in the live database to maximize its accessibility and usability of the information in line with EU FAIR directives. In total 6 methods were used in order to obtain the density, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, comprehensive strength, mass loss and compatibility with molten salts.

2.1 Quantitative methods

1. **(Apparent) Particle density:** An electronic scale with a sensitivity of 0.1 mg was used to weigh the samples. To measure the volume of the solid particles, a 250 ml graduated cylinder with a sensitivity of 2 ml was used. Before each measurement, the system was allowed to rest to ensure that the open pores were filled and to prevent bubble formation. The apparent particle density was then calculated. Measurements were repeated and validated using a scale (0.1mg) and the density measurement apparatus based on Archimedes principle.
2. **Specific heat capacity:** Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was used to perform several measurements on particle powders. Aluminum crucibles were used for clinker, roof tiles, and hollow bricks, while alumina crucibles were used for the metal slags. Each run began with baseline and sapphire standard measurements, followed by the relevant samples. The procedure included heating the samples to 100°C for 10 minutes before each measurement to ensure they were free of moisture. The heating rate for all samples was 20 K/min, and the measurement temperature range was 0–550°C. The raw DSC data were processed in-house and the Cp value was calculated. The experiments were performed in air atmosphere.
3. **Thermal conductivity:** A Hot Disc analyzer was used to measure thermal conductivity. The measurements were conducted inside an enclosed measurement cell. Two solid particle pieces, flat on at least one side, were placed in the cell to ensure proper thermal contact with the TPS sensor. The TPS analyzer was connected to a humidifier, and the measurement cell was submerged in a temperature-controlled oil bath. Measurements were carried out at 25°C and 40°C, with relative humidity (RH) maintained below 10% and 5%, respectively. Two different particle pairs were tested, with five measurements performed at each temperature for each pair.

4. **Comprehensive strength:** A compression test was conducted on bulk material using a plastic container to hold the sample. The material was compacted under a controlled load using a mechanical press, with a maximum load of 25 kN. Force and displacement were recorded throughout the test to evaluate the material's compressive behavior. Each run was stopped when the lateral expansion of the material nearly caused the plastic container to fail. Since the materials varied significantly in shape, resulting in differences in packing behavior, all particles were either tested as received or crushed to a consistent size range of 5–30 mm to minimize variability.
5. **Mass loss:** A Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was performed on the samples to assess its thermal stability and decomposition behavior. The analysis was conducted over a temperature range of 20°C to 800°C. The samples were heated at a rate of 20K/min, and mass changes were recorded throughout the process. This allowed for the identification of different stages of weight loss, such as moisture evaporation, decomposition, or oxidation, and provided insights into the material's composition and thermal stability. The results helped to characterize the thermal behavior and identify any volatile components or residue content in the sample.

2.2 Qualitative methods

6. **Compatibility with Molten salts:** Samples were placed in alumina crucibles as whole particles and were fully covered with solid (premelted for mixing purposes) ternary molten salt (Yara MOST). Then the samples were placed in a high-temperature furnace and kept at 400 degC for 60 h continuously. The samples were then removed and visually inspected.

3 Key results

3.1 Live database

A Open-access material property inventory database is available online and accessible through the following link: [e-LITHE Material Summary D2.6.xlsx](#)

The database contains results from the characterizations as shown in the following figures (screenshots of the information within the database). Results as well as raw data received from the instruments are included in the live database for the main 3 waste ceramic materials. In addition, results for the 3 metallic slags are also shown in this comparative portal for potential TES solid filler materials.

3.1.1 Density

As illustrated in the first sheet of the database (Figure 1) the apparent density (including open pores) of the 3 ceramics is similar and clinker has the highest density nearly reaching 2500 kg/m³. The roof tiles and hollow bricks tested have an apparent density of approximately 2250 kg/m³. For reference, the brass and steel slags show reasonably higher densities while copper slags have a similar density to the 3 ceramics.

Figure 1: Density results in live database (screenshot)

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3.1.2 Specific heat capacity

The specific heat capacity as measured in the temperature range between 0 °C and 550°C is shown in the second sheet of the database. All materials show an increase of their specific heat capacity with increasing temperatures. Clinker and roof tiles have a specific heat capacity that surpasses 1 kJ/(Kg·K) at above 450°C while hollow bricks have lower specific heat capacity up to about 0.85 kJ/(Kg·K).

Figure 2: Specific heat capacity results in live database (screenshot)

3.1.3 Thermal conductivity

The obtained thermal conductivity varies significantly for the 3 ceramic materials as shown in the 3rd sheet of the database and Figure 3. Clinker shows the higher conductivity of approximately 1.5 W/m²K, followed by roof tiles at 0.8 W/m²K and hollow bricks at 0.5 W/m²K. The performed tests between 25°C and 40°C do not show a relevant dependency of the thermal conductivity with respect to the working temperature. However, testing at higher temperatures are planned during T3.2 for further validation of such assumption.

Figure 3: Thermal conductivity results in live database (screenshot)

3.1.4 Compressibility

The compressibility of the 6 samples tested is presented in the 4th sheet of the database and Figure 4. In this case, all 3 ceramics have a similar performance with hollow bricks being the most compressible material in bulk compression.

Figure 4: Compression test results in live database (screenshot)

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3.1.5 Mass loss and thermogravimetric analysis

Figure 5 illustrated the thermogravimetric analysis result sheet in the live database, outlining the main transition happening in the materials and the overall mass loss of the samples. In this case, roof tiles and clinker are outperforming most other materials by showing a total mass loss below 1% up to 800°C, similar to brass slags. Hollow bricks and copper slags present a similar trend with about 2-4% mass loss at 800°C. However, for both hollow bricks and copper slags almost no mass loss is registered up to 500°C, suggesting their potential use within lower temperature ranges. Steel slags lose approximately 10% of their initial mass up to 800°C. It should be highlighted that these values present the TGA results after only the first thermal cycle. Further testing after multiple thermal cycles will be performed in T3.2 and later reported to understand how mass loss progresses in typical TES working conditions.

Figure 5: Thermogravimetric analysis results in live database (screenshot)

3.1.6 Compatibility with ternary molten salts

Finally, the last sheet of the database contains information about the waste material compatibility with ternary molten salts (Yara MOST). Such test have been performed as molten salts are currently one of the most widely spread material for TES application and their exploitation in thermocline units where part of the MS is replaced by solid media is receiving more and more interest. For such application it is a key relevance to first

understand the level of compatibility between the salts and the solids to ensure that not major chemical reaction occurs.

The results showed that most materials were not visibly affected by the interaction with Yara MOST salt at high temperatures. However, hollow bricks seemed to be fully penetrated by the salt which gave them a decomposed and spongy appearance, while the ash samples clearly went through a chemical reaction.

Figure 6: Molten salts compatibility results in live database (screenshot)

4 Conclusions

This deliverable provides a comprehensive characterization of various waste and reference materials to evaluate their suitability for potential applications, particularly as TES solid fillers. Key properties such as density, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, compressive strength, mass loss, and compatibility with molten salts were analyzed using a range of quantitative and qualitative methods. These characterizations are shown as a live database available online ([eLITHE Material Summary D2.6.xlsx](#)), that will be used in the following tasks within WP3 and will be updated with additional material data.

The results indicate that the ceramic waste materials exhibit consistent densities, with clinker demonstrating the highest values. For comparison, metallic slags were included as reference materials and generally showed higher densities, except for copper slag, which aligns more closely with the ceramics. Specific heat capacity measurements reveal that clinker, roof tiles, and hollow bricks display reasonable thermal storage potential, with hollow bricks exhibiting the highest capacity. Thermal conductivity varies among the ceramics, with clinker outperforming the others.

In terms of mechanical performance, all ceramic samples demonstrated comparable compressibility, with hollow bricks being the most compressible. Thermogravimetric analysis highlighted the superior thermal stability of clinker and roof tiles, which displayed minimal mass loss under high temperatures, while the reference steel slags exhibited significant weight reductions. Compatibility tests with molten salts showed that most ceramic materials remained unaffected, although hollow bricks were structurally altered, and ash samples underwent chemical reactions.

Overall, this work highlights the distinct characteristics of the ceramic waste materials and their potential applicability in high-temperature environments. The inclusion of metallic slags as reference materials provides valuable benchmarks for comparison, contributing to the development of sustainable material solutions.

This work serves as a basis for later activities planned in WP3. Further material characterization including consecutive thermal cycles will be performed in the context of T3.2 and the potential storage design to be integrated within the ceramic industries and production lines to maximize flexibility will be performed in T3.3.

